

Consent and Characterization Form

We created this form to characterize the participants that attended the focus group sessions. The first page of the form detailed the purpose of the study and asked respondents if they agreed to participate voluntarily. Participants who agreed to take part in the study had to answer the following questions:

- What is your education level?
- How many years of work experience do you have?
- How many projects involving Machine Learning components have you worked on?
- Based on your professional experience, do you identify yourself more as a data scientist or a software engineer?
- How would you rate your proficiency in data science?
- How would you rate your proficiency in software engineering?